

VARIATIONAL PRINCIPLE FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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In a previous paper, a system of nonlinear differential equations and boundary conditions governing the macroscopic behavior of composite materials modeled by interpenetrating solid continua, was derived. The derivation utilized the classical procedure of defining field vectors and determining the equations relating them by applying energy and momentum conservation theorems. The dissipation and the associated thermodynamics were included. In this paper a variational principle is presented, which is shown to yield the aforementioned system of equations and boundary conditions in the absence of dissipation and heat flow.